

Biamperometric Vanadimetric Determination of Iron(II) and Cobalt (II)

D. Singh and Uma Bhatnagar

Amperometric titration method with two indicator electrodes, now generally known as biamperometric method, has been applied with success for determination of equivalence in large number of monotitrations¹⁻³. A review of literature shows that examples of the redox amperometric titration of binary mixtures available are inadequate and meagre. Recently we succeeded in extending the applicability of this method in determination of various elements in their binary mixtures⁴. The present communication reports the results of successive determination of iron (II) and cobalt (II) present together in solution.

The solutions of ammonium vanadate and ferrous ammonium sulphate were prepared and standardized by the usual methods. Cobalt sulphate solution was standardized as recommended by Laitinen and Burdett⁵. All other chemicals used were c.p. grade. Titrations were carried out on the basis of stepwise oxidation of ferrous and cobaltous ions with a circuit similar to that described by Foulk and Bawden⁶ and Stone and Scholten⁷. Two similar platinum electrodes were immersed into a titration cell, and a constant voltage of the order of 50-100 mV was applied to these electrodes. The titration cell was a 100 ml beaker with a tightly fitting rubber stopper with necessary holes for the platinum electrodes and burette. The reaction mixture consisting of known quantity of ferrous and cobalt sulphate solution in 2.0 N sulphuric acid medium, was taken in the cell and the titrant was added from a 2 ml semimicroburette with 0.01 ml divisions. Galvanometer deflexions were noted after successive additions of the titrant. When the oxidation of Fe (II) was complete, corresponding to the stoichiometric reaction, enough EDTA was added to complex Fe (III) and Co (II), lowering the redox potential of the latter to a point where it becomes titrable with the oxidant. The medium was then adjusted to 0.5 N with respect to sulphuric acid and the applied potential altered to 100 mV; the titration was continued till the indicator current for the oxidation of Co (II) established the end point. Experiments were repeated at least twice for the concordant results.

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Equivalence point was determined graphically from the usual plots of galvanometer deflexions *versus* volume of the titrant added. A typical curve is shown in Fig. 1. The summarised results are given in Table I.

FIG. 1 Biamperometric titration of 5.16 mg Fe(II) and 3.11 mg Co(II) present together in solution.

TABLE I

Determination of Fe (II) and Co (II) in presence of each other

Amount of Fe (II), mg			Amount of Co (II), mg		
Taken	Found	Difference	Taken	Found	Difference
25.81	25.81	± 0.00	16.65	16.65	± 0.00
10.32	10.36	+0.04	6.66	6.60	-0.06
5.16	5.16	± 0.00	8.20	8.13	-0.07
5.16	5.16	± 0.00	3.13	3.11	-0.02
2.58	2.60	+0.02	1.39	1.37	-0.02

An inspection of the data returned in Table I show that the successive determination of iron (II) and cobalt (II) can be accomplished successfully and the results obtained are reproducible and satisfactory.

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